

Effect of azolla and N on rice grain and straw yield

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We evaluated the relative advantage of using azolla *A. pinnata* as a supplemental source of N alone or in combination with N fertilizer in a pot experiment, 1988 wet season. Soil was silty clay loam, with pH 7.4, 1.03% organic C, 0.07% total N, 3 ppm available P, 0.78 meq exchangeable K/100 g soil, CEC 21 meq/100 g soil, and ECE 0.12%. Single superphosphate at

25 mg P/kg soil was applied basally to all pots.

Two levels of urea N, 30 mg N/kg soil and 60 mg N/kg soil, and one level of azolla N, 2.05 mg N/kg soil, were used in a randomized complete block design with four replications.

Fresh azolla, with 93.4% moisture content and (dry weight basis) 4.15% N, 0.45% P, 4.38% K, 0.35% Ca, and 1.42% Na was incorporated 1 d before transplanting rice cultivar IR8-5.

Azolla alone and with urea stimulated growth and significantly increased grain yield (see table). The order of yield increases was 30 mg N/kg

Effect of azolla and N on rice straw and grain yields. Tando Jam, Pakistan, 1988 wet season.

Treatment (per kg soil)	Straw yield (g/pot)	Grain yield (g/pot)
No N	21.96 e	8.24 e
750 mg fresh azolla	27.84 c	10.68 c
30 mg N	26.36 d	9.84 d
30 mg N + 750 mg fresh azolla	30.36 a	12.92 a
60 mg N	28.92 b	11.92 b

soil plus azolla > 60 mg N/kg alone > azolla alone > 30 mg N/kg alone > no N. Straw yield increased significantly with azolla. □

Disease management

Effect of N on bacterial leaf streak (BLS) and bacterial blight (BB) diseases in some scented rice varieties

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Damage from BB caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* and BLS caused by *X. campestris* pv. *oryzicola* depends on the cultivar and on crop management practices. Degree of cultivar susceptibility and duration, N application method, and prevailing weather conditions influence the pattern of disease buildup. BLS becomes severe during incessant rain; BB increases gradually and spreads irrespective of weather.

We studied disease buildup in scented rice cultivars Basmati 370, Pakistan Basmati, T412, IET8580, IETS579, and Badshabhog under four N levels during 1988 wet season, in a random block design with two replications. Plot size was 2.25 × 4 m. N as urea was applied in 30-kg increments, from 0 to 90 kg N/ha, 50% at transplanting, 25% 20 d after transplanting, and 2.5% at panicle initiation. Disease was scored at 10-d intervals from 1 mo after transplanting

to panicle initiation. Severity was estimated as the percentage of leaf area damaged in each plot.

All six varieties were susceptible to BLS and BB, with disease severity depending on N level. Percentage of infected leaf area for both disease, varied among varieties. The analysis of variance was significant for N level, variety, and N × variety interaction for both diseases.

BLS incidence during early crop growth stages was severe in Basmati

1. Buildup of BLS and BB diseases in 4 rice varieties at 4 N levels. Cuttack, India, 1988 wet season.

370, IET8580, and Badshabhog, with 10 to 35% damage to leaf area, depending on N level; BLS was only 0-5% in Pakistan Basmati, IET8579, and T412. At 60 and 90 kg N/ha, disease severity increased between 35 and 45 d after transplanting (DT), with a steep decline thereafter (Fig. 1). This may be due to abundant availability of N initially, coupled with favorable weather conditions. Continuous rainfall during the season increased

2. Weekly averages of maximum and minimum temperature, rainfall, relative humidity, and sunshine hours during crop growth. Cuttack, India, 1988 wet season.